

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XIX. Analogues of Homopteroecarpin and Related Compounds

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Chromeno-(3', 4'-2, 3)-coumarones have been synthesised from the related coumarins and then catalytically reduced to chromano-(3', 4'-2,3)-coumarans having a *cis* junction.

In this paper are described our experiments to synthesise chromano-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarans of the type (V) which bear close resemblance to chromano-(3' 4'-2,2)-coumaran, the latter forming the ring structure of homopteroecarpin (I) or pterocarpin of established constitution (McGookin *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 787; Späth and Schlager, *Ber.*, 1940, 73, 1; Robertson and Whalley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1440). Such a synthesis was obviously desirable not only in the interest of preparing analogues of homopteroecarpin but also for securing products with known stereochemical disposition at the junction of the reduced rings because the nature of ring-fusion in the pterocarpins is still undefined.

The chromano-coumarans have been synthesised from coumarino-(3', 4'-2,3)-coumarones (II), the latter having been synthesised by King *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1672) by von Pechmann's method by the condensation of *m*-dihydroxyphenols and ethyl β -coumaranone-2-carboxylates. On reduction with lithium aluminium hydride the lactone group of (II) was smoothly reduced to the phenolic alcohol (III), the furan ring remaining unaffected in the reduction. This is in contrast to the reduction of coumarino-(3', 4'-3,2)-coumarones in which the simultaneous hydrogenation of the furan ring takes place (Chat-

terjea and Dhoubhadel, unpublished results). The cyclisation of (III) by phosphorus tribromide and subsequent treatment with alkali (cf. Benneville and Connor, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **62**, 883) was unsuccessful on account of extensive formation of polymeric products, whereas attempted cyclisation with sodium acetate—acetic anhydride led only to the formation of a diacetate. The desired cyclisation however, took place when a solution of the phenolic alcohol in diethylene glycol was boiled, the period of boiling being sometimes critical. By this method a fairly consistent yield of 7'-methoxy-, 5',7'-dimethoxy-, 6,7'-dimethoxy-, and 6,5',7'-trimethoxy-chromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarones were obtained.

6,7'-Dimethoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone (IV:R=R'=OMe at 6 and 7') is related to dehydrohomopteroearpin. In common with all the chromenes of this series, this compound was converted into the corresponding pyrylium salt (structure VII) on treatment with triphenylmethyl perchlorate (cf. Bonthron and Reid, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2773; Chatterjea and Mukherjee, *Experientia*, 1960, **16**, 439); the compound was also readily

oxidised by ferric chloride in acetic acid to the related pyrylium ferrichloride. On treatment with bromine vapour in acetic acid, a crimson solution was obtained with the separation of a crystalline deep red product. This is undoubtedly due to the formation of the quinonoid dibromide (VIA or VIB), in which both the resorcinol nuclei become partly quinonoid. The compound loses hydrogen bromide very slowly and passes into the pyrylium salt. This change may be brought about quickly in presence of acetone. This behaviour is also shown by 6,5',7'-trimethoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone, in which the methoxyl groups of the resorcinol and phloroglucinol nuclei are in conjugation. On the other hand, 7'-methoxychromeno- and 5',7'-dimethoxychromenocoumarones gave a transient coloration with bromine with the ready separation of the pyrylium bromides. The formation of a dibromide, mentioned above, recalls the behaviour of deoxythrimetylrazilone (Perkin *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1504) which also forms an unstable dibromide and passes into trimethoxybrazilium salt.

The chromenes described above are smoothly reduced by palladised charcoal in acetic acid to *cis*-chromano-(3', 4'-2,3)-coumarans (V) and as these products do not contain any benzyloxy linkage, further hydrogenolysis is not possible as in the case of the pterocarpins (cf. McGookin *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of the chroman (V: R = R' = OMe at 6 and 7') is very similar to that of homopterocarpin and different from that of its ring-fusion isomeride (isohomopterocarpin). Although this signifies that the former may have a *cis* junction, further direct experimental evidence is necessary to establish the point. Work in this direction is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.'s are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were taken in ethanol solution and measured in a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer. Several analyses of pyrylium perchlorates could not be carried out due to explosion in the combustion tube.

Ethyl 6-Methoxy- β -coumaranone-2-carboxylate.—A solution of ethyl 5-methoxy-2-ethoxycarbonylphenoxyacetate (16.0 g.) in dry purified benzene (150 c.c.) was added to powdered sodium (1.28 g.) and the mixture refluxed gently for 2 hours on a water bath. The sodium salt separating was dissolved in sufficient water and the aqueous layer was acidified to afford the crude ester (10 g.) which crystallised from petroleum ether in colorless plates (9.5 g.), m.p. 117° (King *et al.* report m.p. 112°), showing a green ferric reaction in ethanol. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 5.1. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₂O₅: C, 61.0; H, 5.1%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-coumarone.—A suspension of 7-methoxycoumarono-(2',3',-3,4)-coumarin (King *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) (1.8 g.) in dry ether (50 c.c.) was stirred at the room temperature for 2 hours with lithium aluminium hydride (0.4 g.) with proper exclusion of atmospheric moisture and then left overnight. The mixture was carefully decomposed with H₂SO₄ (dil.) and the ethereal solution on working up yielded a viscous liquid, which solidified when rubbed with benzene. On crystallisation from benzene the *hydroxymethyl compound* (1.2 g.) was obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. 106° (evolution of gas at 170-90°). (Found: C, 70.9; H, 5.1. C₁₆H₁₄O₄ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2%). The *diacetyl derivative*, prepared by heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 5.2. C₂₀H₁₈O₆ requires C, 67.8; H, 5.1%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4,6-methoxyphenyl)-coumarone was similarly prepared from 5,7-dimethoxycoumarono-2', 3'-2, 4)-coumarin and obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. 112° from benzene; yield 80%. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 5.6. C₁₇H₁₅O₅ requires C, 68.0; H, 5.3%). λ_{infl} 237-39 m μ (log ϵ 4.0) and 260-62m μ (log ϵ 3.7). The *diacetate* crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 108°, depressed to 96° on admixture with the original diol. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 5.2. C₂₁H₂₀O₇ requires C, 65.6; H, 5.2%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methoxycoumarone.—6,7'-Dimethoxycoumarono-(2',3'-3,4)-coumarin (m.p. 226°) (1.0 g.) was dissolved in excess of dry ether (400 c.c.) and added to an excess of lithium aluminium hydride (0.8 g.) in ether (50 c.c.); the mixture was stirred at the room temperature for 3 hours. On working up in the usual manner, the *hydroxymethyl compound* (0.8 g.) separated from benzene in reddish prisms, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 5.3. C₁₇H₁₆O₅ requires C, 68.0; H, 5.3%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxycoumarone was similarly prepared from 6', 5, 7-trimethoxycoumarono-(2', 3'-3, 4)-coumarin (m.p. 255°) and obtain-

ed from benzene in fine prisms, m.p. 168°; yield 50%. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 5.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.4; H, 5.5%).

7'-Methoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone.—A solution of 2-hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-coumarone (1.0 g.) in pure diethylene glycol (30 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 25 minutes. During boiling slow separation of water was noted. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, extracted with ether, and washed with alkali. After drying ($MgSO_4$), ether was removed to yield the *chromene* (0.6 g.), which crystallised from ethanol in voluminous fluffy needles, m.p. 69-71°. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%). λ_{max} , 231 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.41), 265 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.03), and 301 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.84).

The compound exhibits a deep red coloration with sulphuric acid. On treating the solution of the compound in acetic acid with bromine vapour, the solution becomes transient red with the separation of a yellow solid (pyrylium bromide). A solution of the compound in boiling acetic acid on treatment with one molecular proportion of triphenylmethyl perchlorate gave *7'-methoxycoumarono-(2,3-3',4')-benzopyrylium perchlorate* as brownish yellow crystals, m.p. 220° (explosion). On crystallisation from acetic acid the compound deteriorates and a brownish product is obtained, m.p. 215° (explosion).

5',7'-Dimethoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone was similarly prepared and obtained from ethanol in colorless crystals, m.p. 105-106°, showing a red coloration with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%). λ_{max} 220 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.46) and 272 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.03). The corresponding *pyrylium perchlorate* was obtained as orange-red needles, m.p. 232° (decomp.). (Found: C, 54.1; H, 3.7. $C_{17}H_{13}O_6Cl$ requires C, 53.6; H, 3.4%).

6,7'-Dimethoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone.—A solution of 2-hydroxymethyl-3-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methoxycoumarone (0.2 g.) in diethylene glycol (5 c.c.) was boiled for only 2 minutes. The product was worked up as before to give the *chromene* (0.1 g.), which crystallised from ethanol in small prisms, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%). λ_{max} 242 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.44), 248 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.44), 271 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.84), and 290 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.98).

The compound develops with sulphuric acid a light pink colour, exhibiting a strong green fluorescence and with strong nitric acid it shows a crimson colour. With bromine vapour a solution of the compound in acetic acid forms an attractive crimson solution with the separation of an unstable crimson, crystalline solid. The red colour very slowly fades away and changes to light yellow. This change takes place quickly on adding a few drops of acetone.

On boiling a solution of the compound in acetic acid with crystalline ferric chloride, the solution turns red with the separation of a fine crystalline precipitate of *6',7'-dimethoxycoumarono-(2',3'-3,4)-benzopyrylium ferrichloride*. This was collected, washed with a small quantity of acetic acid, and obtained as a light orange crystalline mass, m.p. 215° (decomp.). (Found: C, 42.1; H, 3.0. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4FeCl_4$ requires C, 42.6; H, 2.7%)

The corresponding *perchlorate* was prepared by boiling a solution of the *chromene* (0.05 g.) in dry acetic acid (2 c.c.) with triphenylmethyl perchlorate (0.05 g.) for 1 minute. The resulting deep green fluorescent solution on cooling deposited the brownish pyrylium salt, which was collected and washed with acetic acid, m.p. 239° (explosion).

6,5,7'-Trimethoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone—This *chromene* was prepared as above, the period of heating being reduced to 1 minute. The compound crystallised from ethanol in light colorless needles, m.p. 127°; yield, 85%. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.2%). λ_{max} 242 m μ (log ϵ 4.40) and 288 m μ (log ϵ 3.96). The compound develops a dark pink colour with sulphuric acid and a crimson solution with bromine vapour in acetic acid. The corresponding *pyrylium perchlorate* was obtained as before in greyish brown plates, m.p. 231° (decomp.). (Found: C, 53.2; H, 4.1. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5Cl$ requires C, 52.6; H, 3.7%).

cis-7'-Methoxychromano-(3',4'-2,3)-coumaran.—A solution of 7'-methoxychromeno-(3',4'-2,3)-coumarone (0.2 g.) was hydrogenated in acetic acid in presence of palladised charcoal (0.2 g., 5%) at the room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The absorption of hydrogen was complete in 3 hours. The *chroman* (0.15 g.) crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 5.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5%). λ_{max} 282 m μ (log ϵ 3.58). The compound develops a dark brown colour with sulphuric acid. The chroman also gave the related pyrylium salt, m.p. 220°, mentioned before, on treatment with triphenylmethyl perchlorate. On heating the compound with palladised charcoal, a small quantity of a material was obtained which gave a red coloration with sulphuric acid, indicating that the compound might be readily dehydrogenated.

cis-6,7'-Dimethoxychromano-(3',4'-2,3)-coumaran was similarly prepared from the corresponding chromene by hydrogenation and obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 125° from ethanol. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%). λ_{max} 287 m μ (log ϵ 3.84).

cis-6,5',7'-Trimethoxychromano-(3',4'-2,3)-coumaran was prepared by the catalytic hydrogenation of the related chromene and obtained from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 104°. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.8%). λ_{max} 286 m μ (log ϵ 3.63).

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